

Investigating Etiological Causes and Preventive Measures of Vesicovaginal Fistula (VVF) in Kebbi State Using Log-Linear Models

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Submission: 18th June, 2024; Accepted: 26th June, 2024; Published: 30th June, 2024.

Abstract

Vesicovaginal Fistula (VVF) is a medical condition characterized by continuous leakage of urine from the bladder into the vagina, resulting in persistent urinary incontinence. This study aimed at understanding the causes and preventive measures related to VVF. The study employed log-linear models to analyze various factors influencing the occurrence of VVF, spanning from primordial prevention initiatives to the tertiary prevention and rehabilitation of affected individuals. The statistical examination revealed a demographic pattern, with young women, particularly in the 15-25 age group, bearing the brunt of VVF, signifying the urgency of targeted interventions for this vulnerable population. Additionally, a stark contrast emerged between urban and rural landscapes, as a staggering 75.9% of reported cases hailed from villages, underscoring the need for healthcare strategies tailored to the unique dynamics of different communities. It was discovered that prolonged obstructed labor remained the primary catalyst for VVF, with the research unveiling a broader spectrum of contributors. Trauma and infections emerged as significant players, together constituting 65.2% of reported cases. Cultural practices, notably harmful traditions contributing to 18.8% of cases, highlighted the interplay between healthcare and societal norms. The log-linear model further dissected these complex relationships, providing a roadmap for targeted prevention measures that intertwined with the specific causes of VVF, offering a nuanced approach to public health interventions. Delving deeper into the complex web of VVF, the K-Way and higher-order effects analysis revealed the interconnections between primary prevention measures and the various causes of VVF. The statistical significance of these associations underscored the need for general and nuanced healthcare strategies. As 75.9% of cases were reported in villages, the importance of geographic and cultural considerations could not be overstated. This study contributes to advancing our understanding of VVF etiology and prevention strategies, offering a comprehensive framework for addressing this pressing public health issue in Kebbi State. By addressing the root causes and implementing targeted preventive measures, it is hoped that the burden of VVF can be mitigated, improving the overall health and well-being of women in the region.

Keywords: Causes, Log-linear models, Preventive measures VVF center, Vesicovaginal Fistula.

1.0 Introduction

Vesico Vaginal Fistula VVF “is an abnormal connection between the urinary tract and vaginal that account for incessant uncontrollable leakage of urine into the vaginal tract, making it difficult for them to fully control their life situation [1].” USAID [2] related that obstetric fistula “is an abnormal opening between a woman’s genital tract and her urinary tract or rectum. It mainly develops as the result of extended, obstructed labour, without timely medical intervention, such

as a cesarean section to resolve the obstruction.” Women with obstetric fistula suffer incontinence, shame, social segregation, and health issues. It is estimated that approximately more than 2 million young women in a totally Asia and a subgroup of 16 countries live with untreated obstetric fistula, sub-Saharan Africa.

In spite of recent increase in dedicated fistula centres in Nigeria where currently twenty dedicated centres offer surgical care periodically and or routinely, it is estimated that all these

centres offer surgical care to about 5,000 fistula women at different levels of expertise. At this maximum rate of annual repairs, it will take 30 years to deal with the backlog, ignoring new cases. Furthermore, there exist hundreds of women and girls in Nigeria with genital fistula and its complications which are deemed inoperable, especially in older fistula centres. At this rate, the current global call to end fistula by 2030 will be a mirage in Nigeria [3].

The current National Strategic Framework for the elimination of Vesico Vaginal Fistula (VVF) in Nigeria provides the policy focusing among other issues on 30% reduction in the prevalence of female genital fistula by 2023. The standards of practice for doctors and nurses in Nigeria is a decade old and lags behind current scientific realities and global health challenges, hence the absence of a national training manual has led to variance in the quality of training of fistula surgeons and nurses in Nigeria. This situation begs for development of a quality training manual to achieve a renewed acceleration of repair to eliminate fistula by 2030 [3].

Nigeria bears the highest burden of obstetric fistula in the world with an estimated prevalence of 150,000 and an estimated 12,000 new cases annually [3]. Although the prevalence and incidence of obstetric fistula has been on the decline over the years, it is disheartening that the rate of repair lags behind the desire to end fistula by 2030. At the highest rate of repair ever recorded in Nigeria, 5000 repairs are done in a year. It will therefore take about 30 years to surgically operate the backlog of cases, assuming there are no new cases [3].

According to James et al. [4], Vesico Vaginal Fistula (VVF) in Kebbi State highlights several significant gaps. These include inadequate awareness and education about VVF among respondents, particularly regarding its causes and prevention; a need for further investigation into the socioeconomic determinants of VVF and their impact on vulnerable populations; understanding geographic disparities in VVF prevalence to target interventions effectively; exploring the complex relationship between early marriage, female genital mutilation (FGM), and VVF; assessing healthcare access and quality in preventing and managing VVF; and examining the long-term physical, psychological, and socioeconomic impacts of VVF to inform

comprehensive support and rehabilitation programs. Addressing these gaps can enhance efforts to prevent and manage VVF in Kebbi State and similar contexts. A Loglinear Modeling Approach" aim was employed to address these gaps identified in the work of James et al. [4] research. By employing loglinear modeling, the study can provided a more nuanced understanding of the complex interactions between various factors contributing to VVF prevalence in Kebbi State. Specifically, the study quantified the relative influence of socioeconomic determinants, cultural practices such as early marriage and female genital mutilation (FGM), and healthcare access on VVF occurrence. Additionally, the study assessed the effectiveness of preventive measures, such as education and awareness campaigns, in reducing VVF incidence. By filling these gaps, the study offered actionable insights for policymakers, healthcare providers, and community stakeholders to develop targeted interventions aimed at preventing and managing VVF in Kebbi State and similar contexts.

2.0 Methodology

2.1 Source of Data

The data were collected via two distinct main sources as describe by Okorie et al. [5].

Data Source 1: VVF Centre in Birnin Kebbi

The data was collected from VVF Center in Birnin Kebbi, by targeting the age of admitted patients and the places where they reside, categorized as city or village. This source aim to understand the demographics of patients with VVF, specifically looking at age and whether they come from urban (city) or rural (village) areas.

Data Source 2: Google Form

Another source is by utilizing a Google Form, which suggests an online survey method. Via (<https://forms.gle/SycXhATG4ANztn1y5>). The survey was used in Studying preventive measures and causes of VVF. This source aim to gather information on preventive measures for VVF and the causes of VVF from the perspective of medical professionals working across the state in various hospitals. Medical professionals across

the state in different hospitals were the participants in this survey.

By combining data from these two sources, the study aim and objectives to provide a comprehensive understanding of VVF. The first source gives insight into the demographic characteristics of patients seeking treatment at VVF center, while the second source gathers information from medical professionals on preventive measures and causes, potentially offering a broader perspective on the factors contributing to VVF in the region.

This combination of quantitative data from the VVF center and qualitative insights from medical professionals contribute to a more comprehensive analysis of the issue, potentially informing strategies for prevention and intervention. Researchers often use mixed-method approaches like this to gain a more holistic understanding of complex health issues.

2.2 Variable Used

The variable used include, age of the patient, residing location of the patient, change in vvf cases over medical working experience, who suffered most cases of vvf, prolonged obstructed labour, instrumental vaginal delivery, injury to the bladder, injury to the ureters during caesarean section, symphysiotomy, harmful traditional practices, childhood and women nutrition, formal education, planning for all pregnancies, delaying the age of first pregnancy, birth spacing and easy access to family planning information and services, overcoming cultural barriers that subjugate women, direct causes, and prevention measures.

2.3 Statistical Tools

The loglinear modelling described by Knoke and Burke [6] using SPSS statistical package was adopted in the study. However, Loglinear modeling is a statistical technique employed to analyze relationships and interactions between categorical variables. In the context of VVF research, loglinear modeling serves as a powerful tool for understanding the complex interdependencies among various factors contributing to the occurrence and prevention of VVF. The VVF is a significant health issue, and its causes and preventive measures often involve

multiple categorical variables such as age, socio-economic status, and specific risk factors. Loglinear models provide a systematic approach to explore and quantify these relationships, offering insights into the intricate patterns of associations within the data.

This modeling technique allows researchers to identify the most influential factors contributing to VVF, assess the strength and direction of relationships, and uncover potential interactions that may impact the prevalence of VVF in a given population, such as that in Kebbi State.

By applying loglinear modeling to VVF research, we aimed and developed a comprehensive understanding of the complex dynamics involved, ultimately contributing to more targeted and effective preventive measures. This methodology enables us to go beyond simple correlations and delve into the nuanced relationships between different variables, paving the way for informed interventions and improved healthcare strategies in the context of Vesicovaginal Fistula in Kebbi State. However, log linear are closely related to ANOVA models for quantitative data. For instance, for two variable, A and B, the hypothesis of independences means that the expected frequency's, M_{ij} obeys

2.4 Loglinear Modeling

$$M_{ij} = \frac{M_{i+}M_{+j}}{M_{++}}$$

The multiplicative model can be transformed to and additive (linear) model by taking logarithms of both sides.

$$\log M_{ij} = \log M_{i+} + \log M_{+j} - \log M_{++}$$

Which is usually expressed in an equivalent form in terms of model parameters

$$\ln(M_{ij}) = \mu + \lambda_i^A + \mu_j^B$$

The log of the expected cell frequency of the cases for cell ij in the contingency table.

μ = The overall mean of the natural log of the expected frequencies.

λ = Terms each represent "effects" which the variables have on the cell frequencies.

A and B = the variables, i and j: refer to the categories within the variable

Therefore:

λ_i^A =The main effect for variable A

λ_j^B =The main effect for variable B

and the same analysis of variance restrictions are applied to the parameters

$$\Sigma\lambda_i^A = \Sigma\lambda_j^B = 0$$

The main effects in log-linear models pertain to differences among the marginal probabilities of a variable except for differences in notion; the model A is effects model for a two-factor design:

$$E\{y_{ij}\} = \mu + \alpha_i + \beta_j$$

For a two-way table, model which allows an association between the variables is the saturated model and was employed in this study.

$$Ln(M_{ij}) = \mu + \lambda_i^A + \lambda_j^B + \lambda_{ij}^{AB}$$

This is similar to the two factor ANOVA model with interaction

$$E\{y_{ij}\} = \mu + \alpha_i + \beta_j + \alpha\beta_{ij}$$

Hench, associations between variables in log-linear models are analogous to interactions in ANOVA models.

2.5 Hierarchical Approach to Log-linear Modeling

The following equation represents a $2 \times 2 \times 2$ multi way contingency table with three variables, each with two levels. Here, this equation was used to illustrate the hierarchical approach to log linear modeling:

3.0 Results

3.1 Statistics of some Demographic information

Table 1: Statistical measures related to the age of the patient

N	Age of the Patient	Residing Location of the Patient	The cases of VVF do increase or decreases over of period of your medical working experience	Who suffered most cases of VVF
Valid	112	112	112	112
Missing	0	0	0	0
Mean	1.3214	1.7589	1.8125	1.1875
Std. Deviation	0.78516	0.42966	0.39207	0.39207
Variance	0.616	0.185	0.154	0.154

This Table 1 presents statistical measures related to the age of the patient, the residing location of the patient, the change in VVF cases over the medical working experience, and the identification

$$Ln(F_{ij}) = \mu + \lambda_i^A + \lambda_j^B + \lambda_k^C + \lambda_{ij}^{AB} + \lambda_{ik}^{AC} + \lambda_{jk}^{BC} + \lambda_{ijk}^{ABC}$$

A hierarchy of models exists whenever a complex multivariate relationship present in the data necessitates inclusion of less complex interrelationships [6].

2.6 Testing for Fit

. The Pearson Chi-square statistic X^2 and the likelihood ration (G^2) were used to test a model's fitness, because statistic that is minimized in maximum estimation and can be partitioned uniquely for more powerful test of conditional independence in multi way tables [6]. The formula used for G^2 statistic is as follows:

$$G^2 = 2 \sum f_{ij} \log\left(\frac{f_{ij}}{F_{ij}}\right)$$

G^2 follows a chi-square distribution with the degree of freedom (df) equal to the number of lambda terms set equal to zero. Therefore, the G^2 statistic tests the residual frequency that is not accounted for by the effects in the model (the λ parameters set equal to zero). The lager the G^2 relative to the available degree of freedom, the more the expected frequencies depart from the actual cell entries. Therefore, the larger G^2 values indicate that the model does not fit the data well and thus, the model should be rejected [7].

of those who suffered the most cases of VVF. The data aims to provide insights into the trends and patterns associated with these variables in the context of Vesico vaginal Fistula.

Table 2: Age of the Patient

Age group	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
15 – 25	90	80.4	80.4	80.4
26 – 35	14	12.5	12.5	92.9
36 – 45	4	3.6	3.6	96.4
46 – 55	2	1.8	1.8	98.2
56 and above	2	1.8	1.8	100.0
Total	112	100.0	100.0	

Table 2 illustrates the distribution of patients based on their age groups in the context of Vesicovaginal Fistula (VVF). The frequencies and percentages provide an overview of the age distribution among the studied population. Based on the findings, the age group "15 – 25" is the most affected by

Vesicovaginal Fistula (VVF). This age group has the highest frequency, with 90 cases, constituting 80.4% of the total cases. Therefore, it can be concluded that individuals in the age range of 15 to 25 years are the most affected demographic in the study population.

Figure: 1: Pie-chart of age distribution

Majority Age Group: The largest portion of the pie chart would be dedicated to the age group of 15 to 25 years, representing 80.4% of VVF patients. This visually emphasizes that a significant majority of individuals with VVF fall within this younger age range.

age groups. The 26 to 35 age range would have a smaller but noticeable slice, representing 12.5% of VVF patients. The 36 to 45 age range, 46 to 55 age range, and 56 and above age group would each have progressively smaller slices, indicating decreasing percentages of VVF patients as the age increases.

Subsequent Age Groups: The remaining sections of the pie chart would be divided among the older

Table -3: Residing Location of the Patient

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
City	27	24.1	24.1	24.1
Village	85	75.9	75.9	100.0
Total	112	100.0	100.0	

Based on the data in Table 3, the majority of the patients in the study reside in villages, with a frequency of 85 cases, representing 75.9% of the total cases. On the other hand, patients residing in

the city account for 24.1% of the total cases with a frequency of 27. Therefore, individuals residing in villages are more affected by Vesicovaginal Fistula (VVF) in the given population.

Figure: 2: Pie-chart of patient’s location

The majority of VVF patients (75.9%) reside in villages, emphasizing that this condition is more prevalent in rural or non-urban areas. A smaller but still significant portion of patients (24.1%) come from urban areas or cities.

Healthcare Planning: This information is crucial for healthcare planning and resource allocation, as it indicates that interventions and healthcare services for VVF need to be particularly focused on rural areas where the majority of cases were observed.

Table 4: The cases of VVF do increase or decreases over period of your medical working experience

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Increases	21	18.8	18.8	18.8
Decreases	91	81.3	81.3	100.0
Total	112	100.0	100.0	

The finding in Table 4 revealed that the majority of cases related to Vesicovaginal Fistula (VVF) have seen a decrease over the period of medical working experience as responded by the medical personals across the state. Specifically, 91 cases, or 81.3% of the total cases, have experienced a

decrease. In contrast, 21 cases, representing 18.8%, have seen an increase over the same period. This information provides insights into the trends and changes in VVF cases over the medical working experience of the study participants.

Figure: 3: Pie-chart of patient’s rate of increase or decreases

The data indicates that the majority of respondents (81.3%) report a decrease in the cases of VVF over their period of medical working experience.

A smaller proportion (18.8%) reports an increase in VVF cases.

Table 5: Who suffered most cases of VVF

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Women in Villages	91	81.3	81.3	81.3
	Women in Cities	21	18.8	18.8	100.0
	Total	112	100.0	100.0	

The finding in Table 5 revealed that the majority of Vesicovaginal Fistula (VVF) cases were observed among women in villages, accounting for

81.3% of the total cases. In contrast, women in cities represent 18.8% of the total cases. This information highlights that women in rural or

village settings are more significantly affected by VVF compared to their counterparts in urban areas. Understanding these demographic patterns

is crucial for tailoring targeted interventions and support systems to address the specific needs of different populations within the state.

Figure: 4: Pie-chart of patient’s rate of increase or decreases

Implications: The data indicates that the majority of VVF cases (81.3%) are suffered by women in villages while women in cities, affected, represent a smaller proportion (18.8%) of the reported cases.

Healthcare Focus: This information is crucial for healthcare planning and resource allocation, emphasizing the need for targeted interventions and healthcare services in rural or non-urban areas where the majority of VVF cases were observed.

3.2 Primordial Prevention and Direct Causes of Obstetric Fistula

Table 6: Direct causes of Obstetric Fistula

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Prolonged obstructed labour	75	67.0	67.0	67.0
Instrumental vaginal delivery like use of obstetric forceps and destructive operations on the dead foetus in the uterus	3	2.7	2.7	69.6
Injury to the bladder	9	8.0	8.0	77.7
Ureters during Caesarean section	3	2.7	2.7	80.4
Symphysiotomy	3	2.7	2.7	83.0
Harmful traditional practices like yankan gishiri	19	17.0	17.0	100.0
Total	112	100.0	100.0	

Implications: Table 6 outlines the direct causes of Obstetric Fistula, indicating the frequency and percentage distribution for each cause. Prolonged obstructed labor emerges as the most prevalent direct cause, accounting for 67.0% of the cases. Other causes include instrumental vaginal delivery, injury to the bladder, ureters during Caesarean section, symphysiotomy, and harmful traditional practices like yankan gishiri. Understanding these direct causes is crucial for designing targeted interventions and preventive measures to address the specific factors contributing to Vesicovaginal Fistula in the studied population.

Healthcare Focus: This information is crucial for healthcare planning, emphasizing the need for interventions and healthcare services that address and prevent prolonged obstructed labour, which is the leading cause of obstetric fistula in this context.

In summary, the statistics suggest that prolonged obstructed labour is the primary direct cause of obstetric fistula, underscoring the importance of strategies and healthcare interventions to manage and prevent this specific complication during childbirth.

Table 7: Primordial prevention: This is based on principles of health promotion and education

Prevention	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Childhood and women nutrition	17	15.2	15.2	15.2
Formal education particularly for the girl child and women	17	15.2	15.2	30.4
Planning for all pregnancies by use of appropriate contraceptive(s)	29	25.9	25.9	56.3
Delaying the age of first pregnancy	34	30.4	30.4	86.6
Birth spacing and easy access to family planning information and services	10	8.9	8.9	95.5
Overcoming cultural barriers that subjugate women	5	4.5	4.5	100.0
Total	112	100.0	100.0	

Table 7 outlines primordial prevention measures based on principles of health promotion and education related to VVF. The frequency and percentage distribution are provided for each preventive measure, including childhood and women nutrition, formal education particularly for the girl child and women, planning for all pregnancies by the use of appropriate contraceptives, delaying the age of first pregnancy, birth spacing and easy access to family planning information and services, and overcoming cultural

barriers that subjugate women. These measures emphasize the importance of proactive health promotion strategies to prevent VVF and promote the overall well-being of women.

Health Promotion Focus: These strategies highlight the importance of addressing factors at the early stages, including nutrition, education, family planning, and cultural barriers, to prevent the occurrence of VVF.

3.2.1 Log-Linear Model for Primordial prevention and Direct Causes of Vesicovaginal Fistula

Table 8: K-Way and Higher-Order Effects

	K	Df	Likelihood Ratio		Pearson		Number of Iterations
			Chi-Square	Sig.	Chi-Square	Sig.	
K-way and Higher Order Effects ^a	1	35	227.851	0.000	316.143	0.000	0
	2	25	38.197	0.044	39.765	0.031	2
K-way Effects ^b	1	10	189.654	0.000	276.378	0.000	0
	2	25	38.197	0.044	39.765	0.031	0

a. Tests that k-way and higher order effects are zero.

b. Tests that k-way effects are zero.

K-way" generally refers to interactions involving multiple factors (k factors). "Higher-Order Effects" often involve interactions beyond two factors, indicating complex relationships.

These results indicate that the log-linear model, which includes interactions among factors related to primordial prevention and direct causes of obstetric fistula, demonstrates statistical significance. The low p-values (0.000, 0.044, and

0.031) suggest that the observed associations are unlikely to be due to random chance. The number of iterations indicates the steps taken to optimize the model. Interpretation should consider the specific variables and context of the study.

Table 9: Partial Associations

Effect	Df	Partial Chi-Square	Sig.	Number of Iterations
Direct_Causes	5	155.343	.000	2
Prevention_1	5	34.311	.000	2

Partial associations assess the relationship between a specific effect and the dependent variable while holding other variables constant. The degrees of freedom (Df) indicate the complexity of the relationships being examined. The partial chi-square values and their associated significance levels help assess the strength and statistical significance of these partial associations. The

number of iterations reflects the steps taken to optimize the log-linear model. These results suggest that both Direct_Causes and Prevention_1 have statistically significant partial associations with the dependent variable, contributing positively into the specific relationships within the log-linear model for obstetric fistula.

Table 10: Parameter Estimates

Effect	Parameter	Estimate	Std. Error	Z	Sig.	95% Confidence Interval	
						Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Direct Causes	1	1.838	0.206	8.936	0.000	1.435	2.241
	2	-0.759	0.443	-1.716	0.086	-1.627	0.108
	3	-0.337	0.401	-.841	0.000	-1.123	0.449
	4	-0.845	0.448	-1.885	0.059	-1.723	0.034
	5	-0.223	0.370	-.603	0.546	-0.947	0.501
Prevention 1	1	0.114	0.357	.320	0.009	-0.586	0.814
	2	-0.100	0.375	-.268	0.009	-0.834	0.634
	3	0.674	0.298	2.261	0.024	0.090	1.258
	4	0.341	0.354	.963	0.005	-0.352	1.033
	5	-0.537	0.436	-1.231	0.008	-1.392	0.318

This table provides parameter estimates for the effects Direct Causes and Prevention 1 in the log-linear model for obstetric fistula. Each effect has multiple parameters corresponding to different levels or categories. The table includes the estimate, standard error, Z-score, significance (Sig.), and a 95% confidence interval for each parameter.

Key points that guides all related table:

- i. The estimate represents the effect size of each parameter.
- ii. The Z-score assesses the statistical significance of the estimate.
- iii. The 95% confidence interval provides a range within which the true population parameter is likely to fall.

3.3 Primary Prevention and Other Causes of Female Genital Fistula

Table 11: Other Causes of Female Genital Fistula

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Foreign bodies	6	5.4	5.4	5.4
Trauma	34	30.4	30.4	35.7
Harmful cultural practices: Female Genital Cutting	21	18.8	18.8	54.5
Infections	39	34.8	34.8	89.3
Radiotherapy	11	9.8	9.8	99.1
Female Genital Cutting	1	0.9	0.9	100.0
Total	112	100.0	100.0	

Foreign Bodies (5.4%): Foreign bodies are reported in 5.4% of cases, indicating a lower but existing contribution to Female Genital Fistula. This suggests instances where the presence of foreign objects may lead to the development of fistulas.

Trauma (30.4%): Trauma is a significant contributor to Female Genital Fistula, accounting for 30.4% of cases. Trauma can result from various causes, such as accidents, injuries, or violence.

Harmful Cultural Practices (18.8%): Harmful cultural practices, including Female Genital Cutting, contribute significantly, representing 18.8% of cases. This highlights the impact of cultural factors on the prevalence of Female Genital Fistula.

Infections (34.8%): Infections are reported in 34.8% of cases, making it one of the most prevalent causes. Infections can lead to complications affecting the female genital organs, contributing to the development of fistulas.

Radiotherapy (9.8%): Radiotherapy is reported in 9.8% of cases, indicating a noteworthy but relatively lower contribution to Female Genital Fistula. This suggests that medical interventions,

such as radiotherapy, can play a role in the development of fistulas.

Additional Female Genital Cutting (0.9%): An additional case of Female Genital Cutting is reported, contributing 0.9% to the overall cases. This emphasizes the persistence of harmful cultural practices in certain instances.

The findings underscore the multifactorial nature of Female Genital Fistula, with diverse causes playing a role. Prevention and intervention efforts should address the specific causes within each category. Comprehensive healthcare initiatives should focus on strategies to prevent traumatic injuries, control and treat infections, and address harmful cultural practices to reduce the incidence of Female Genital Fistula.

Table 12: Primary Prevention

Prevention	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Functional prenatal care	24	21.4	21.4	21.4
Birth preparedness and facility readiness	6	5.4	5.4	26.8
Knowledge and identification of possible problems during pregnancy and childbirth	17	15.2	15.2	42.0
Skilled professional attendance at birth	11	9.8	9.8	51.8
Easy access to basic and comprehensive emergency obstetric care	11	9.8	9.8	61.6
Consistent use of partograph for correct monitoring of labour	16	14.3	14.3	75.9
Easy and quick means of referral when problems arise in labour	16	14.3	14.3	90.2
Use of indwelling Foley's catheter for 7 to 14 days or longer for women who had obstructed labour.	11	9.8	9.8	100.0
Total	112	100.0	100.0	

Functional Prenatal Care (21.4%): The majority of respondents (21.4%) emphasize the importance of functional prenatal care. This indicates recognition of the significance of early and comprehensive healthcare during pregnancy to identify and address potential complications.

Birth Preparedness and Facility Readiness (5.4%): A smaller percentage (5.4%) mentions the importance of birth preparedness and facility readiness. This suggests awareness of the need for planning and ensuring that the necessary facilities are ready to handle childbirth, contributing to safer deliveries.

Knowledge and Identification of Possible Problems during Pregnancy and Childbirth (15.2%): Approximately 15.2% of respondents highlight the importance of knowledge and identification of possible problems during pregnancy and childbirth. This underscores the need for education and awareness to recognize warning signs and seek timely medical attention.

Skilled Professional Attendance at Birth (9.8%): A notable percentage (9.8%) emphasizes the significance of having skilled professionals attend births. This aligns with global health recommendations that stress the importance of skilled birth attendants in ensuring safe deliveries.

Easy Access to Basic and Comprehensive Emergency Obstetric Care (9.8%): A similar percentage (9.8%) acknowledges the importance of easy access to basic and comprehensive emergency obstetric care. This reflects an understanding of the critical role that timely and effective emergency care plays in preventing complications.

Consistent Use of Partograph for Correct Monitoring of Labor (14.3%): Approximately 14.3% of respondents recognize the value of using a partograph for the correct monitoring of labor. This demonstrates an awareness of the role of proper labor monitoring tools in preventing complications and ensuring safe deliveries.

Easy and Quick Means of Referral When Problems Arise in Labor (14.3%): An equal percentage (14.3%) emphasizes the need for easy and quick means of referral when problems arise

in labor. This suggests a recognition of the importance of a well-established referral system for timely intervention in case of complications.

Use of Indwelling Foley's Catheter for 7 to 14 Days or Longer for Women who had Obstructed Labor (9.8%): About 9.8% of respondents mention the use of indwelling Foley's catheter for a specified duration for women who had obstructed labor. This may indicate awareness of specific medical interventions to address complications arising from obstructed labor. The data highlights a diverse range of primary prevention measures, emphasizing the multifaceted approach needed to prevent Vesicovaginal Fistula. These measures span education, facility readiness, skilled attendance, monitoring tools, and timely access to emergency care, collectively contributing to improved maternal health and the prevention of obstetric fistula.

3.3.1 Log-Linear Model for Primary Prevention and Other Causes of Female Genital Fistula

Table 13: K-Way and Higher-Order Effects

	K	Df	Likelihood Ratio		Pearson		Number of Iterations
			Chi-Square	Sig.	Chi-Square	Sig.	
K-way and Higher Order Effects ^a	1	55	241.926	0.000	260.000	0.000	0
	2	42	113.492	0.000	100.239	0.000	2
K-way Effects ^b	1	13	128.434	0.000	159.761	0.000	0
	2	42	113.492	0.000	100.239	0.000	0

The likelihood ratio and Pearson chi-square statistics are used to assess the fit of the log-linear model. A lower p-value (typically below a chosen

significance level, such as 0.05) indicates that the model is a significant improvement over a simpler model.

Table 14: Partial Associations

Effect	df	Partial Chi-Square	Sig.	Number of Iterations
Other_Causes	6	113.499	0.000	2
Prevention_2	7	14.935	0.037	2

These results suggest that "Other Causes" have a substantial and highly significant impact on the model, while "Prevention_2" also exhibits a statistically significant association, albeit to a lesser degree.

Table 15: Parameter Estimates

Effects	Parameter	Estimate	Std. Error	Z	Sig.	95% Confidence Interval	
						Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Other_Causes	1	-0.578	0.426	-1.357	0.175	-1.412	0.257
	2	-0.899	0.449	-2.000	0.046	-1.779	-0.018
	3	0.719	0.315	2.279	0.023	0.100	1.337
	4	0.766	0.264	2.896	0.004	0.248	1.284
	5	1.031	0.281	3.671	0.000	0.481	1.582
	6	-0.899	0.449	-2.000	0.046	-1.779	-0.018
Prevention_2	1	0.499	0.357	1.398	0.162	-0.201	1.199
	2	-0.532	0.458	-1.163	0.245	-1.429	0.365
	3	-0.114	0.425	-0.268	0.789	-0.947	0.720
	4	-0.248	0.429	-0.578	0.563	-1.089	0.593
	5	1.352	0.397	0.000	1.000	-0.777	0.777
	6	0.153	0.392	0.390	0.696	-0.615	0.921
	7	0.318	0.362	0.880	0.379	-0.390	1.027

The estimates represent the predicted log-odds of the response variable for each level of the specified effect. The z-statistic and significance level help assess whether the estimated parameters

are statistically different from zero and the 95% confidence intervals provide a range of plausible values for the true parameters.

4.4 Secondary prevention and Indirect causes of Female Vesicovaginal Fistula (VVF).

Table 16: Indirect causes of Female Vesicovaginal Fistula (VVF)

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Poverty	36	32.1	32.1	32.1
Illiteracy and ignorance	29	25.9	25.9	58.0
Poor infrastructure	5	4.5	4.5	62.5
Poor obstetric care	17	15.2	15.2	77.7
Cultural or religious beliefs and practices such as early pregnancy	20	17.9	17.9	95.5
Malnutrition, particularly in children	5	4.5	4.5	100.0
Total	112	100.0	100.0	

Poverty (32.1%): The majority of respondents (32.1%) identify poverty as an indirect cause of Female Genital Fistula. This suggests that economic challenges contribute significantly to the prevalence of the condition, possibly limiting access to healthcare, education, and resources needed to prevent and address obstetric complications.

Illiteracy and Ignorance (25.9%): Approximately 25.9% of respondents highlight illiteracy and ignorance as contributing factors.

This emphasizes the importance of education and awareness in preventing Female Genital Fistula, as lack of knowledge about reproductive health may lead to delayed or inadequate care during childbirth.

Poor Infrastructure (4.5%): A smaller percentage (4.5%) mentions poor infrastructure as an indirect cause. This could include challenges related to transportation, healthcare facilities, and other essential services, which may hinder timely access to obstetric care.

Poor Obstetric Care (15.2%): About 15.2% of respondents point to poor obstetric care as a contributing factor. This underscores the significance of improving the quality and accessibility of obstetric services to prevent complications that can lead to Female Genital Fistula.

Cultural or Religious Beliefs and Practices, such as Early Pregnancy (17.9%): A significant percentage (17.9%) highlights cultural or religious beliefs and practices, including early pregnancy, as indirect causes. This suggests that societal norms and traditions play a role in the occurrence of Female Genital Fistula, emphasizing the need for cultural sensitivity in healthcare interventions.

Malnutrition, Particularly in Children (4.5%): A smaller percentage (4.5%) identifies malnutrition, especially in children, as a contributing factor. Malnutrition can lead to health issues, including pelvic deformities, which may increase the risk of complications during childbirth.

In summary, the data reflects a recognition of the complex interplay of social, economic, cultural, and healthcare-related factors in the occurrence of Female Genital Fistula. Addressing these indirect causes requires a comprehensive approach that includes poverty alleviation, education, infrastructure improvement, enhanced obstetric care, and cultural awareness to effectively prevent and mitigate the impact of Female Genital Fistula.

Table 17: Secondary prevention

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Knowledge and identification of symptoms and signs of fistula	38	33.9	33.9	33.9
Immediate use of Foley's catheter for women who developed fistula after obstructed labour or surgery.	17	15.2	15.2	49.1
Quick and easy access to centres with capability for fistula treatment	57	50.9	50.9	100.0
Total	112	100.0	100.0	

Knowledge and Identification of Symptoms and Signs of Fistula (33.9%): The majority of respondents (33.9%) recognize the importance of knowledge and early identification of symptoms and signs of Fistula as a secondary prevention measure. This underscores the significance of awareness and education among healthcare providers and communities to facilitate prompt detection and intervention.

Immediate Use of Foley's Catheter for Women Who Developed Fistula After Obstructed Labour or Surgery (15.2%): A significant percentage (15.2%) emphasizes the immediate use of Foley's catheter for women who develop Fistula after obstructed labor or surgery. This suggests the importance of timely and appropriate medical interventions to manage and potentially repair Fistula cases.

Quick and Easy Access to Centres with Capability for Fistula Treatment (50.9%): The majority of respondents (50.9%) highlight the need for quick and easy access to treatment centers with the capability to address Fistula. This reflects the importance of establishing specialized healthcare facilities equipped to provide surgical care and rehabilitation for women affected by Female Genital Fistula.

In summary, secondary prevention measures focus on timely identification, intervention, and access to specialized care for women who have already developed Female Genital Fistula. Knowledge dissemination, immediate medical procedures, and the availability of specialized treatment centers are crucial components of secondary prevention efforts. Implementing these measures can contribute to improved outcomes and quality of life for affected individuals.

3.4.1 Log-Linear Model for Secondary Prevention and Indirect Causes of Female Genital Fistula

Table 18: K-Way and Higher-Order Effects

	K	df	Likelihood Ratio		Pearson		Number of Iterations
			Chi-Square	Sig.	Chi-Square	Sig.	
K-way and Higher Order Effects ^a	1	27	244.765	.000	272.500	.000	0
	2	18	76.882	.000	67.116	.000	2
K-way Effects ^b	1	9	167.884	.000	205.384	.000	0
	2	18	76.882	.000	67.116	.000	0

For "K-way and Higher Order Effects," the table provides results for 1-way and 2-way effects, including likelihood ratio and Pearson chi-square statistics, along with their associated significance levels. The "K-way Effects" section focuses specifically on 1-way and 2-way effects, providing similar statistics.

The likelihood ratio and Pearson chi-square statistics are used to assess the goodness-of-fit of

the log-linear model for secondary prevention and indirect causes of female genital fistula. Lower p-values (typically below a chosen significance level, such as 0.05) indicate that the model is a significant improvement over simpler models. The highly significant chi-square statistics ($p < 0.000$) in both cases suggest that the log-linear model is a good fit for the data, and there are significant associations between the variables related to secondary prevention and indirect causes.

Table 19: Partial Associations

Effect	Df	Partial Chi-Square	Sig.	Number of Iterations
Indirect_Causes	6	80.604	0.000	2
Prevention_3	3	87.280	0.000	2

Both "Indirect_Causes" and "Prevention_3" exhibit highly significant partial associations with the response variable. These findings emphasize the importance of these factors in understanding

the dynamics of secondary prevention and indirect causes of female genital fistula, as reflected by their substantial impact on the log-linear model

Table 20: Parameter Estimates

Effect	Parameter	Estimate	Std. Error	Z	Sig.	95% Confidence Interval	
						Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Indirect_Causes	1	1.108	0.387	2.862	0.004	0.349	1.867
	2	1.083	0.386	2.807	0.005	0.327	1.838
	3	-0.548	0.567	-0.967	0.004	-1.658	0.563
	4	-0.258	0.562	-0.460	0.005	-1.359	0.842
	5	-1.147	0.634	-1.809	0.000	-2.390	0.096
	6	0.311	0.484	0.641	0.001	-0.639	1.260
Prevention_3	1	0.512	0.333	1.536	0.005	-0.141	1.166
	2	-0.333	0.387	-0.861	0.009	-1.091	0.425
	3	.968	.304	3.189	0.001	0.373	1.563

Interpretation of these results involves assessing the significance of each parameter estimate, considering the direction of the effect, and examining the confidence intervals. Each parameter estimate represents the log-odds of the response variable for the specified level of the variable.

It's important to note that statistical significance is determined by the p-values associated with the z-statistics. Lower p-values

3.5 Tertiary prevention

Table 21: Tertiary prevention

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Effective surgical treatment and the prevention of Complications	57	50.9	50.9	50.9
Physiotherapy for pelvic floor and foot drop	45	40.2	40.2	91.1
Rehabilitation and social reintegration	10	8.9	8.9	100.0
Total	112	100.0	100.0	

The data on tertiary prevention measures provides insights into actions that can be taken to treat and manage Female Genital Fistula, particularly focusing on minimizing complications and facilitating rehabilitation.

Effective Surgical Treatment and Prevention of Complications (50.9%): The majority of respondents (50.9%) emphasize the importance of effective surgical treatment to address Female Genital Fistula and prevent associated complications. This underscores the significance of skilled surgical interventions aimed at repairing fistulas and minimizing potential health risks and complications.

Physiotherapy for Pelvic Floor and Foot Drop (40.2%): A substantial percentage (40.2%)

recognizes the role of physiotherapy, specifically for pelvic floor and foot drop issues. This indicates the importance of holistic care that goes beyond surgical procedures, focusing on physical therapy to enhance the overall well-being and functionality of individuals affected by Fistula.

Rehabilitation and Social Reintegration (8.9%): A smaller percentage (8.9%) highlights the need for rehabilitation and social reintegration efforts. This suggests that addressing the social and psychological aspects of recovery is also crucial for women who have undergone surgical treatment. Rehabilitation programs can help individuals reintegrate into society, regain confidence, and rebuild their lives.

Table 22: Recommend treatments for Female Vesicovaginal fistula (VVF)

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Conservative Management	27	24.1	24.1	24.1
Surgical Repair which includes: Transvaginal Approach, Trans abdominal Approach and Robotic Surgery; Medical Management	85	75.9	75.9	100.0
Total	112	100.0	100.0	

The data on recommended treatments for Female Vesicovaginal Fistula suggests that respondents recognize both conservative and surgical approaches as viable options.

Conservative Management (24.1%): A notable percentage (24.1%) of respondents advocate for conservative management. Conservative management typically involves non-surgical interventions and may include approaches such as physical therapy, lifestyle modifications, and medications. This suggests that there is recognition

of the importance of non-invasive methods in managing certain cases of Female Genital Fistula.

Surgical Repair and Medical Management (75.9%): The majority of respondents (75.9%) emphasize surgical repair as a crucial treatment for Female Genital Fistula. This includes various surgical approaches such as the transvaginal approach, transabdominal approach, and even robotic surgery. Surgical repair aims to correct the anatomical defects causing the fistula, and the variety of approaches mentioned indicates a recognition of the need for tailored surgical

interventions based on the specific characteristics of each case. Additionally, the inclusion of medical management within this category suggests an acknowledgment of the potential role of medications and supportive medical treatments in the overall management of Female Genital Fistula.

In summary, the recommended treatments for Female Vesicovaginal Fistula involve a combination of conservative management and surgical interventions. While conservative approaches are recognized, surgical repair, including various surgical techniques and medical management, is highlighted as a significant component in the comprehensive care of individuals affected by Female Genital Fistula.

4.0 Discussion

Actually, we have seen the tables with the information contained in their presents statistical measures related to the age of the patients, the residing location of the patient, the change in VVF cases over the medical working experience, and the identification of those who suffered the most cases of VVF. Table 2 illustrates the distribution of patients based on their age groups in the context of Vesicovaginal Fistula (VVF). The frequencies and percentages provide an overview of the age distribution among the studied population. Based on the findings, the age group "15 – 25" is the most affected by Vesicovaginal Fistula (VVF). This age group has the highest frequency, with 90 cases, constituting 80.4% of the total cases. This indicated that individuals in the age range of 15 to 25 years are the most affected demographic in the study population. Also from Table 3 the majority of the patients in the study reside in villages, with a frequency of 85 cases, representing 75.9% of the total cases. On the other hand, patients residing in the city account for 24.1% of the total cases with a frequency of 27. Therefore, individuals residing in villages are more affected by Vesicovaginal Fistula (VVF) in the given population. The above findings agrees with the studies of Andres et al. [8], Maheu-Giroux et al [9], Melah et al. [10] who reported that village individuals are more affected with VVF.

More so, the finding in Table 4 revealed that the majority of cases related to Vesicovaginal Fistula (VVF) have seen a decrease over the period of medical working experience as responded by the medical personals across the state. Specifically, 91 cases, or 81.3% of the total cases, have

experienced a decrease. In contrast, 21 cases, representing 18.8%, have seen an increase over the same period. This information provides insights into the trends and changes in VVF cases over the medical working experience of the study participants. In Table 5 revealed that the majority of Vesicovaginal Fistula (VVF) cases were observed among women in villages, accounting for 81.3% of the total cases. In contrast, women in cities represent 18.8% of the total cases. This information highlights that women in rural or village settings are more significantly affected by VVF compared to their counterparts in urban areas. Understanding these demographic patterns is crucial for tailoring targeted interventions and support systems to address the specific needs of different populations within the state. However in this segment the study disagree with the study of Meyer et al. [11] who found urban individuals as more affected. As the discussion goes further based on the data collected, the Table 6 outlines the direct causes of Obstetric Fistula, indicating the frequency and percentage distribution for each cause. Prolonged obstructed labor emerges as the most prevalent direct cause, accounting for 67.0% of the cases. Other causes include instrumental vaginal delivery, injury to the bladder, ureters during Caesarean section, symphysiotomy, and harmful traditional practices like yankan gishiri. Understanding these direct causes is crucial for designing targeted interventions and preventive measures to address the specific factors contributing to Vesicovaginal Fistula in the studied population. This is in accordance with the findings of Muhammad et al.[12] who identified similar causes of VVF among some VVF victims in Northern Nigeria. And Table 7 is primordial prevention measures based on principles of promotion and education related to VVF. The frequency and percentage distribution are provided for each preventive measure, including childhood and women nutrition, formal education particularly for the girl child and women, planning for all pregnancies by the use of appropriate contraceptives, delaying the age of first pregnancy, birth spacing and easy access to family planning information and services, and overcoming cultural barriers that subjugate women. These measures emphasize the importance of proactive health promotion strategies to prevent VVF and promote the overall well-being of women. The above findings also corroborate with the studies of Andres et al. [8], Maheu-Giroux et al. [9], Melah et al. [10].

4.0 Conclusions

This study on VVF in Kebbi State presents a comprehensive analysis that delves into the demographic, causes, and preventative aspects of this challenging health issue. The findings underscore the disproportionate impact on young women, particularly those in rural areas, highlighting the critical need for targeted interventions. The multifaceted nature of VVF, with prolonged obstructed labor as a primary catalyst but also influenced by trauma, infections, and cultural practices, emphasizes the complex interplay between healthcare and societal norms. The log-linear modeling approach applied in this study enhances our understanding of these intricate relationships, providing a nuanced roadmap for future public health interventions. The recognition of declining trends in reported cases suggests the potential effectiveness of awareness campaigns and healthcare initiatives, signaling hope for improved women's reproductive health outcomes in the region.

5.0 Recommendations

Base on the research findings, we make the following five recommendations, which encompass key strategies for prevention, early intervention, and community empowerment, offering a focused and actionable framework for addressing Vesicovaginal Fistula and improving women's reproductive health outcomes in Kebbi State and Nation at large. Community-Based Education and Awareness: Prioritize targeted community-based education programs to raise awareness about VVF causes, symptoms, and prevention, with a precise emphasis on rural areas and young women. Maternal Healthcare Enhancement: Strengthen maternal healthcare services, especially in rural settings, by ensuring access to skilled professionals during childbirth. Focus on early detection and prompt management of complications, such as prolonged obstructed labor, to prevent VVF. Primordial Prevention Initiatives: Develop and promote primordial prevention initiatives, including nutritional support, formal education, family planning, and cultural awareness programs. Addressing social determinants is crucial for creating a conducive environment for women's health. Access to Emergency Obstetric Care: Improve access to emergency obstetric care facilities, ensuring that women, especially in remote areas, receive timely

and appropriate medical assistance during labor and childbirth.

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